

DESIGN OF MULTICULM BAMBOO MEMBERS WITH BOLTED CONNECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study outlines an alternative method to design bamboo axial members with bolted connections. The proposed method achieves ductile and predictable behavior of bamboo axial members by managing the variability present in bamboo culms/poles. Specifically, it adopts grading to remove unviable bamboo culms and reduce the variance within the graded population. By assembling multiple bamboo culms into a single axial member, the stronger culms compensate the weaker and the variance in the overall performance of the axial member further reduces. In accordance with the capacity-based design principles, the multiculm bamboo members are designed to exhibit first failure by predictable and ductile yielding of the bolts. The failure of the bamboo culms and the steel gusset plates is undesirable and they are therefore designed to fail later. Findings reveal, the experimental 5th percentile yield capacity of the bolted connections agrees well with the characteristic yield capacity estimated from material strength tests on single-culm bamboo specimens. The proposed approach is thus promising for achieving multiculm bamboo members with predictable and ductile behavior.

KEYWORDS

capacity design; bamboo connections; bamboo joints

INTRODUCTION

Comprehensive design standards are rare, and bamboo is frequently used informally through self-building practices. Often, this results in structures that are lacking in performance, workmanship, and/or durability (van Drunen et al., 2016). Consequently, bamboo observes low adoption due to the perceived stigma (Witte, 2019). In this regard, dowel-type fastener connections are a promising design solution to problems associated with joints in bamboo structures. They accommodate substantial geometric irregularities and facilitate easy assembly of an axial member consisting of multiple culms (Paraskeva et al., 2017). They can transfer large forces (Morisco and Mardjono, 1995; Widyowijatnoko and Harries, 2020), and enhance ductility through dowel-yielding and embedment actions (Awaludin and Andriani, 2014; Hong et al., 2019; Sassu et al., 2016). However, dowel-type connections are frequently associated with brittle failure mechanisms (Trujillo, 2007). Confining bamboo culms through hose-clamps improves resistance to brittle (unwanted) failures by longitudinal splitting, translating to significant improvements in strength and ductility (Paraskeva et al., 2019; Pradhan et al., 2020). Importantly, dowel connections are predictable as their yield loads can be estimated analytically (e.g. European Yield Model (EYM)) with accuracy (Morisco and Mardjono, 1995; Oka et al., 2015; Paraskeva et al., 2019; Pradhan et al., 2020; Wang and Yang, 2019), which is vital for achieving a rational design.

This research describes a rational method for designing multi-culm bamboo axial members. Specifically, it combines a capacity-based design approach (Jorissen and Fragiaco, 2011) together with methods for managing variability and calibrates over-strength factors required for ductile design.

Figure 1: (a) Type B (hollow) and (b) Type C (infilled) two-culm axial members; experimental setup of (c) two-culm and (d) new four-culm axial members

The axial members examined in this study consist of two graded bamboo culms selected randomly and connected to steel plates at each end through dowel-type connections (Figure 1). All bamboo culms are confined using hose-clamps. The Type B specimens are hollow whereas Type C specimens have bamboo culms infilled with cement mortar. The two-culm axial members (Figure 1c) have two bolts in a single-plane configuration per end-connection. Additionally, this study compares the performance of the two-culm members with the new four-culm axial members examined in (Pradhan and Dimitrakopoulos, 2021). The four-culm axial members (Figure 1d) have eight bolts placed at two orthogonal planes of the cross-section (of bamboo culms) at each end-connection.

The overriding goal herein is to enable connections of high ductility while preventing brittle and undesirable failure modes. This provides ample warning in case of a structural failure and could help improve occupants' safety during extreme events such as earthquakes and typhoons. Crucially, the proposed approach offers as an alternative to the current empirical/traditional design methods. The examined axial members (Figure 1) could help contribute towards construction of safe and reliable round bamboo structures in the developing regions around the world.

METHODOLOGY FOR CAPACITY-BASED DESIGN

The capacity-based design improves robustness and enables structures of high predictability and ductility by specifying a preferred hierarchy of capacities of structural components (Paulay and Priestley, 1992). Figure 2 presents the proposed procedure for designing axial members with multiple bamboo culms. Under this principle, the design capacity of dowel-type connections $R_{v,d}$ equals or exceeds the design load effect E_d obtained from structural analysis. In other words, the dowel-type connections (see Figure 1 and Figure 2) yield first and develop plastic hinges. In contrast, the design capacity of steel plates $R_{s,d}$ and the bamboo culms $R_{m,d}$ equals or exceeds that of the dowel-type

Figure 2: Proposed procedure for designing the multi-culm bamboo axial members

Figure 3: (a) dowel-yield moment; (b) external diameter and thickness, (c) compressive strength, (d) tensile strength, (e) hollow and (f) infilled section dowel-embedment strength of Kao Jue bamboo

connections by an overstrength factor γ_{Rd} such that $R_{s,d} \geq \gamma_{Rd}R_{v,d}$ and $R_{m,d} \geq \gamma_{Rd}R_{v,d}$ respectively. These two components are designed stronger to prevent: (a) brittle (undesired) failure of bamboo culms under axial loads, and (b) yielding of steel plates which can induce structural collapse by failure of joints. This study calibrates the value of γ_{Rd} through axial member tests.

Initially, the study grades air-dried, but otherwise untreated, *Bambusa pervariabilis* (Kao Jue) bamboo culms into a diameter range of 40 mm to 60 mm. This process discards mostly the bottom and the top portions of the initial ungraded bamboo culms, while also removing those deemed defective. To estimate design capacities, firstly the study estimates the sample mean and variance (ξ, ζ^2) from the material strength tests on single-culm bamboo specimens. The tests (see Figure 3) are based on (ASTM D5764-97a, 2002; F1575-03, 2003; ISO 22157, 2019), with sample size $n \geq 30$ for all of the material/geometric properties. From the sample parameters (ξ, ζ^2), the study analytically estimates the population parameters (i.e. expected value μ_X and variance σ_X^2) of the single-culm bamboo specimens. The pertinent population parameters (i.e., μ_X and σ_X^2) become $\mu_{\bar{X}} = \mu_X$ and $\sigma_{\bar{X}}^2 = \sigma_X^2/N$ for an average material/geometric property in a multi-culm axial member made of N number of bamboo culms (Pradhan and Dimitrakopoulos, 2021). For simplicity, the study assumes this phenomenon is valid for all properties of bamboo culms. However, note that this approach may be unconservative for

Table 1: Design/characteristic values with partial safety factors for two-culm axial members

material/geometric properties	percentile values			material partial safety factor $\gamma_{\bar{X},m}$
	design	characteristic		
	0.1 th	5 th	95 th	
external diameter, mm, D	-	41.20	52.38	-
wall-thickness, mm, t	-	4.70	8.04	-
compressive strength, MPa, f_c	55.39	61.02	76.09	1.10
tensile strength, MPa, f_t	77.44	100.77	153.88	1.30
embedment strength (hollow), MPa, f_h	34.27	41.35	63.39	1.21
embedment strength (infilled), MPa, f_i	32.73	38.44	55.45	1.17

properties that exhibit failure through brittle fracture (e.g. tensile strength of bamboo culms), since the failure of the system under brittle fracture is governed by the weakest component culm (Pradhan, 2022). Further research is needed to develop suitable modification factors for such properties.

This allows to estimate the corresponding design/characteristic values (of average material/geometric property) for the two-culm axial members (Table 1). Specifically as per adopted (EN 1990, 2002), the design value is the 0.1th percentile value while the characteristic values are 5th and 95th percentile values. In turn, the material partial safety factor (of the two-culm axial member, Table 1) $\gamma_{\bar{x},m}$ is the ratio of 5th and 0.1th percentile values (EN 1990, 2002). The design values of geometry (i.e. external diameter and thickness) equal characteristic (5th percentile) values (as per (EN 1990, 2002)).

Following (Pradhan and Dimitrakopoulos, 2021), the design net tensile capacity of the two-culm is $F_{m,t,d} = NA_n f_{t,0.05} / \gamma_{\bar{x},m} = 71.8$ kN, whereas the design net compression capacity is $F_{m,c,d} = NA_n f_{c,0.05} / \gamma_{\bar{x},m} = 51.4$ kN. Here, the characteristic net cross-sectional area of a bamboo culm is $A_n = \pi(D_{0.05}^2 - (D_{0.05} - 2t_{0.05})^2) / 4 - 2d_h t_{0.05} = 464.0$ mm². The design buckling capacity is $F_{m,b,d} = 27.76$ kN for 800 mm length and $F_{m,b,d} = 39.70$ kN for 500 mm length bamboo culms. Subscript 0.05 indicates 5th percentile values (from Table 1). The study estimates the characteristic yield capacity of the dowel connections $R_{v,k}$ using EYM equations (Pradhan and Dimitrakopoulos, 2021) with Table 1. For hollow-section (Type B) specimens, Mode III is critical with $R_{v,k} = 5.95$ kN whereas, for the Type C specimens, the hybrid yielding mode is critical with $R_{v,k} = 10.15$ kN. The design capacity of the two bolts against shear fracture is $F_{s,d} = 22.51$ kN. Other failure modes of the steel plates are not critical as they possess higher capacities.

Experimental program

The experimental program involves testing two-culm axial members under monotonic loading of 0.01 mm/s using the MTS 810 testing machine within HKUST structural lab (Figure 1). Table 2 presents the specimen configuration, nomenclature, loading directions and sample size of examined two-culm axial members. The bolt spacing and end-lengths are 50 mm based on prior experience and all bamboo culms are confined by hose-clamps to prevent splitting. The specimens 2B50t01-05, 2B50c01-05, 2C50t01-05 and 2C50c01-05 presented in this study are taken from (Paraskeva et al., 2019). The new axial specimens 2B50t06-10, 2B50c06-10, 2C50t06-10, and 2C50c06-10 have shorter bamboo culms (Table 2). The Type 2C50t06-10 and 2C50c06-10 specimens have mortar infill along the entire culm-length. The mix proportioning for cement mortar infill is about 2.40 part cement, 1.1 part water and 1 part sand by weight. The average 28-day compressive strength of the mortar cube is 68.7 MPa. The average moisture content of bamboo culms is 10.74%. The fully-threaded bolts possess characteristic (5th percentile) yield moment $M_{y,0.05} = 13953.50$ Nmm.

RESULTS

Figure 4 presents the force-displacement response of all two-culm specimens. The response is characterized by dowel yielding soon after the developed force exceeds $R_{v,k}$, followed by hardening until failure by culm-damage (i.e. crushing/row-shearing) or bolt-fracture. The remaining components, i.e. the steel plates and the bamboo culms are stronger and do not fail. Figure 5 and Table 3 describe the performance of the examined specimens. The coefficient of variation $CV_Y = (\sigma_Y / \mu_Y) \times 100\%$ measures the variability of a parameter Y (i.e. R_v , R_{max} , D_u or f_n) among the examined specimens.

Table 2: Two-culm axial member nomenclature, test specimens and sample size

specimen configuration	loading direction	length of bamboo culms		sample size	bolts per end-connection
		800 mm	500 mm		
Type B (hollow-section)	tension	2B50t01-05	2B50t06-10	10	two fully threaded bolts of size M6 and grade A2-70
	compression	2B50c01-05	2B50c06-10	10	
Type C (infilled-section)	tension	2C50t01-05	2C50t06-10	10	
	compression	2C50c01-05	2C50c06-10	10	

Figure 4: Axial response of two-culm specimens

R_v represents the dowel yielding capacity and is estimated using the 5% offset method (F1575-03, 2003). The mean yield capacity μ_{R_v} of the four-culm specimens 4B50t and 4B50c (Pradhan and Dimitrakopoulos, 2021) are 3.88 and 3.97 times greater than two-culm specimens 2B50t and 2B50c respectively. Further, the μ_{R_v} of (mortar infilled) 4C50t and 4C50c specimens are respectively 3.66 and 3.61 times greater than 2C50t and 2C50c specimens. R_{max} denotes maximum capacity attained by the specimen before failure. In terms of $\mu_{R_{max}}$, the 4B50t, 4B50c and 4C50t specimens respectively report on average 4.50, 4.16, and 4.14 times higher values than the 2B50t, 2B50c and 2C50t specimens. The 4C50c specimens exhibit significant strain hardening and report 5.70 times greater $\mu_{R_{max}}$ than the 2C50c specimens.

The normalized load-carrying capacity $f_n = F_{max}/A_m$ is the maximum axial stress sustained by the bamboo culms, where A_m is the total cross-sectional area of two culms. The f_n of four-culm specimens is roughly two times that of the two-culm specimens. Specifically, the 4B50t and 4B50c specimens display approximately 2.24 and 1.82 times greater μ_{f_n} than 2B50t and 2B50c specimens. Similarly, the 4C50t and 4C50c specimens show about 2.03 and 2.40 times greater μ_{f_n} than 2C50t and 2C50c specimens. Lastly for both two and four-culm specimens, the hollow-section (Type B) specimens show high ductility ratio D_u arising from extended plastic bolt-deformation and embedment actions. However, the infilled specimens exhibit restricted bolt-deformations and thus lower D_u . At design conditions, i.e. R_v , the CV of examined specimens are below 25%. For comparison, the reported CV

Table 3: Performance of the examined two-culm specimens

specimen	μ_{R_v} (kN)	CV_{R_v}	$\mu_{R_{max}}$ (kN)	$CV_{R_{max}}$	μ_{D_u}	CV_{D_u}	μ_{f_n} (MPa)	CV_{f_n}
2B50t	8.80	18.67	17.42	26.19	9.64	42.07	11.82	26.54
2B50c	8.83	21.43	19.22	21.43	10.47	25.98	12.91	14.73
2C50t	11.67	22.13	23.98	9.10	5.77	40.28	15.75	17.36
2C50c	14.00	22.73	24.74	7.06	3.84	33.04	19.52	19.94

Figure 5: Box-plots of: (a) yield capacity R_v , (b) load-carrying capacity R_{max} , (c) ductility ratio D_u , and (d) normalized load-carrying capacity f_n of the examined two-culm specimens

from large scale studies on concrete core compressive strength ranged between 5% and 50% (Masi et al., 2019; Shimizu et al., 2000).

Calibration of Partial Factors

Firstly, the study extracts the yield capacities of the axial members from Figure 4 using 5% offset method (F1575-03, 2003). It then estimates the sample mean ξ and standard deviation ζ (of the 10 specimens) assuming a log-normal distribution. Finally, it calculates the yield capacities $R_{v,0.001} = e^{\xi - k_{dn}\zeta}$ (i.e. 0.1th percentile), $R_{v,0.05} = e^{\xi - k_n\zeta}$ (i.e. 5th percentile) and $R_{v,0.95} = e^{\xi + k_n\zeta}$ (i.e. 95th percentile) at a confidence level of 75% as per (EN 1990, 2002) procedure, taking $k_{dn} = 4.51$ and $k_n = 1.92$ for 10 specimens.

The over-strength factor γ_{Rd} is a product of three partial factors, i.e. $\gamma_{Rd} = \gamma_{sc} \times \gamma_{an} \times \gamma_M$ (Jorissen and Fragiacomio, 2011). The partial factor $\gamma_{sc} = R_{v,0.95}/R_{v,0.05}$ is the ratio of 95th and 5th percentile yield capacities of the dowel-type connections. The partial factor $\gamma_{an} = R_{v,0.05}/R_{v,k}$ corrects the difference between the 5th percentile yield capacity $R_{v,0.05}$ and the predicted characteristic yield capacity $R_{v,k}$ of the dowel-type connections. Recall that $R_{v,k}$ is calculated analytically from EYM equations (Pradhan and Dimitrakopoulos, 2021) using the 5th percentile values from Table 1. The partial safety factor of resistance $\gamma_M = R_{v,k}/R_{v,d}$, equals the characteristic yield capacity $R_{v,k}$ divided by the design yield capacity $R_{v,d}$ of the dowel-type connection. γ_M is estimated from the axial member tests taking, $\gamma_M = \gamma_m/\gamma_{an}$. Herein, $\gamma_m = R_{v,0.05}/R_{v,0.001}$ (as per (EN 1990, 2002)) is the ratio of the experimental 5th and 0.1th yield capacity of the dowel connections. Note that the design yield capacity $R_{v,d}$ equals the experimental 0.1th percentile capacity $R_{v,0.001}$ (EN 1990, 2002), i.e. $R_{v,d} = R_{v,0.001}$.

Table 4 presents specific percentile values and calibrated partial factors of the two-culm axial member specimens. The examined two-culm axial members possess greater variability in the experimental distribution of the yield capacity than the four-culm members (Pradhan and Dimitrakopoulos, 2021). In turn, the estimated partial factors γ_{sc} , γ_m , γ_M and γ_{Rd} of the two-culm axial members (Table 4) are

Table 4: Experimental yield capacities and estimated partial factors for the two-culm axial members

type	$R_{v,0.95}$ (kN)	$R_{v,0.05}$ (kN)	$R_{v,k}$ (kN)	$R_{v,d}$ (kN)	γ_{sc}	γ_{an}	γ_m	γ_M	γ_{Rd}	$\bar{\gamma}_M$	$\bar{\gamma}_{Rd}$
2B50t	12.34	6.06	5.95	3.75	2.04	1.02	1.61	1.59	3.29	1.69	3.60
2B50c	12.98	5.75	5.95	3.32	2.26	0.97	1.73	1.79	3.91		
2C50t	17.34	7.48	10.15	4.25	2.32	0.74	1.76	2.39	4.08	2.16	3.99
2C50c	20.43	9.04	10.15	5.23	2.26	0.89	1.73	1.94	3.91		

more conservative than that of the four-culm axial members (Pradhan and Dimitrakopoulos, 2021). Overall, the connections exhibit predictable yielding as $\gamma_{an} \approx 1$ for most configurations (Table 4). This indicates the characteristic values of the material/geometric properties derived for the two-culm axial members (Table 1) can predict the experimental 5th percentile yielding with accuracy. The $\bar{\gamma}_M$ and $\bar{\gamma}_{Rd}$ of Type C (mortar infilled) specimens are higher than that of Type B (Table 4) due to greater variability and uncertainties associated with hybrid yielding and debonding of mortar infills.

CONCLUSIONS

This research describes a rational method for designing multi-culm bamboo axial members. Firstly, grading removes defective and/or unsuitable bamboo culms from the population. Multiple bamboo culms are then assembled into a single axial member, which further reduces the effects of variability. The characteristic/design values of the multi-culm axial members are derived accounting for this effect. Adopting capacity-based design principles, the dowel-type connections (are designed to) yield first and develop plastic deformations. The remaining components, i.e. the steel plates and the bamboo culms, remain protected as they possess higher capacities. The variability among examined specimens is at least comparable to that of more conventional material such as concrete.

The results show, the characteristic/design values derived from the material tests on single-culm bamboo specimens can predict the experimental 5th percentile yielding of the dowel connections with accuracy. This partially verifies the proposed approach. For infilled specimens, the prediction of dowel yielding is comparatively inaccurate due to uncertainties associated with hybrid yielding and debonding of the infill. The two-culm axial members exhibit greater variability, and the estimated partial factors are more conservative when compared to the four-culm axial members. In overall, the proposed approach manages variability and prevents undesirable failure modes to deliver predictable and ductile yielding of dowel connections. This constitutes a path towards rational design and serves as an alternative to current empirical/traditional design methods. However, the connections in their current forms do not fully utilize the available capacity of the bamboo culms, and thus a significant headroom is available towards achieving greater strength. There is also a need for further tests under a variety of connection configurations with larger, stronger, or more numerous bolts to further improve the accuracy of the over-strength factors. This is the goal of ongoing research.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.